

Venus seen from Mars (local extrema of apparent brightness from 1976-2014)

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An observer stays in a space ship that circles around Mars.

Explanations: mag = stellar magnitude, °= degree, ' = angular minute, " = angular second,

AE= astronomical unit =149598500 km

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance from Venus to Mars [AE]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	Apparent diameter [']	Distance from Venus to Sun [AE]
2.1.- 12.1.1976	-2.92	69-77 increasing	1.71-1.84 increasing	22.82-24.82 decreasing	9.1-9.8 decreasing	0.72
25.8.1976	weaker than +5.00	<1	0.90	1.55	18.6	0.72
4.5.- 23.5.1977	-3.71	65-78 decreasing	1.43-1.64 decreasing	26.17-29.89 increasing	10.2-11.7 increasing	0.72-0.73 increasing
11.8.1977	weaker than +5.00	<1	0.73	1.72	22.9	0.72
26.10.-11.11. 1977	-3.47	65-77 increasing	1.60-1.83 increasing	22.88-26.31 decreasing	9.1-10.4 decreasing	0.71-0.73 increasing
25.6.1978	weaker than +5.00	<1	0.92	1.52	18.2	0.72
13.3.- 18.3.1979	-3.72	66-70 decreasing	1.44-1.50 decreasing	28.83-29.70 increasing	11.1-11.6 increasing	0.73
9.6.1979	weaker than +5.00	<1	0.70	1.94	23.9	0.72-0.73 decreasing
27.8.- 1.9.1979	-3.51	66-71 increasing	1.60-1.68 increasing	25.37-25.38 decreasing	9.9-10.4 decreasing	0.72
24.4.- 25.4.1980	weaker than +5.00	<1	0.93	1.48	18.0	0.72
1.1.- 22.1.1981	-3.71	59-74 decreasing	1.32-1.58 decreasing	27.42-31.05 increasing	10.6-12.7 increasing	0.72-0.73 increasing
5.4.1981	weaker than +4.00	<1	0.68	2.06	24.6	0.73
23.6.- 26.6.1981	-3.55	65-69 increasing	1.55-1.61 increasing	26.48-27.13 decreasing	10.4-10.8 decreasing	0.71-0.72 increasing
23.2.1982	weaker than +5.00	<1	0.94	1.42	17.8	0.72
4.11.-17.11. 1982	-3.70	60-70 decreasing	1.34-1.52 decreasing	28.44-30.73 increasing	11.0-12.5 increasing	0.72-0.73 increasing
31.1.1983	weaker than +4.00	<1	0.67	2.08	24.9	0.73
18.4.- 23.4.1983	-3.59	63-68 increasing	1.48-1.57 increasing	27.14-28.17 decreasing	10.6-11.3 decreasing	0.72
24.12.1983	weaker than +6.00	<1	0.94	1.33	17.8	0.72
4.9.- 11.9.1984	-3.68	61-67 decreasing	1.38-1.48 decreasing	28.90-30.13 increasing	11.3-12.1 increasing	0.72-0.73 increasing
27.11.1984	weaker than +4.00	<1	0.66	1.96	25.3	0.73
4.2.- 26.2.1985	-3.62	57-73 increasing	1.34-1.64 increasing	25.99-29.77 decreasing	10.2-12.5 decreasing	0.71-0.72 decreasing
23.10.1985	weaker than +6.00	<1	0.95	1.23	17.6	0.72
2.7.-8.7.1986	-3.65	62-67 decreasing	1.41-1.50 decreasing	28.48-29.45 increasing	11.1-11.8 increasing	0.72

23.9.1986	weaker than +5.00	<1	0.65	1.71	25.7	0.73
3.12.-21.12.1986	-3.66	58-71 increasing	1.34-1.57 increasing	27.26-30.14 decreasing	10.6-12.5 decreasing	0.71-0.72 decreasing
24.8.1987	weaker than +6.00	<1	0.95	1.11	17.6	0.72
21.4.-8.5.1988	-3.61	59-72 decreasing	1.39-1.62 decreasing	26.38-29.42 increasing	10.3-12.0 increasing	0.72-0.73 increasing
20.7.1988	weaker than +5.00	<1	0.66	1.35	25.3	0.73
30.9.-17.10.1988	-3.69	58-71 increasing	1.32-1.55 increasing	27.64-30.51 decreasing	10.8-12.7 decreasing	0.71-0.73 decreasing
23.6.1989	weaker than +7.00	<1	0.94	0.97	17.8	0.72
12.2.-5.3.1990	-3.57	59-75 decreasing	1.42-1.72 decreasing	24.72-28.82 increasing	9.7-11.8 increasing	0.71-0.73 increasing
16.5.1990	weaker than +6.00	<1	0.67	0.91	24.9	0.73
28.7.-17.8.1990	-3.71	58-73 increasing	1.31-1.57 increasing	27.36-30.81 decreasing	10.6-12.8 decreasing	0.71-0.73 decreasing
23.4.1991	weaker than +7.00	<1	0.94	0.82	17.8	0.72
6.12.-31.12.1991	-3,53	60-79 decreasing	1.47-1.81 decreasing	22.90-28.10 increasing	9.2-11.4 increasing	0.71-0.72 increasing
12.3.1992	weaker than +7.00	<1	0.68	0.45	24.6	0.73
24.5.-18.6.1992	-3.72	59-76 increasing	1.32-1.61 increasing	26.52-30.88 decreasing	10.4-12.7 decreasing	0.72-0.73 decreasing
21.2.1993	weaker than +7.00	<1	0.93	0.65	18.0	0.72
5.10.-22.10.1993	-3.50	65-77 decreasing	1.59-1.82 decreasing	22.98-26.54 increasing	9.2-10.5 increasing	0.71-0.72 increasing
7.1.1994	weaker than +7.00	<1	0.70	<0.01	23.9	0.73
31.3.-9.4.1994	-3.73	67-73 increasing	1.44-1.55 increasing	27.82-29.45 decreasing	10.8-11.6 decreasing	0.72
22.12.1994	weaker than +8.00	<1	0.92	0.46	18.2	0.72
5.8.-14.8.1995	-3.47	70-77 decreasing	1.70-1.84 decreasing	22.71-24.91 increasing	9.1-9.8 increasing	0.71-0.72 decreasing
5.11.1995	weaker than +8.00	<1	0.73	0.40	22.9	0.73
27.1.-15.2.1996	-3.72	67-79 increasing	1.46-1.67 increasing	25.23-29.30 decreasing	10.0-11.4 decreasing	0.72-0.73 decreasing
21.10.1996	weaker than +8.00	<1	0.90	0.25	18.6	0.72
28.5.-11.6.1997	-3.44	71-81 decreasing	1.74-1.94 decreasing	20.74-24.27 increasing	8.6-9.6 increasing	0.71-0.72 decreasing
2.9.1997	weaker than +7.00	<1	0.75	0.74	22.3	0.73
6.12.-12.12.1997	-3.71	75-79 increasing	1.60-1.68 increasing	25.15-26.65 decreasing	9.9-10.4 decreasing	0.72-0.73 decreasing
21.8.1998	weaker than +8.00	<1	0.88	0.02	19.0	0.72
15.3.-13.4.1999	-3.41	69-88 decreasing	1.74-2.11 decreasing	16.89-24.36 increasing	7.9-9.6 increasing	0.71-0.73 decreasing
2.7.1999	schwäche als +6.00	<1	0.78	1.00-1.01 increasing	21.4	0.73
7.10.-1.11.1999	-3.69	77-89 increasing	1.65-1.88 increasing	18.93-25.60 decreasing	8.9-10.1 decreasing	0.72-0.73 decreasing
19.6.2000	weaker than +7.00	<1	0.86	0.23	19.4	0.72
7.1.-6.2.2001	-3.39	72-91 decreasing	1.80-2.17 decreasing	15.20-23.44 increasing	7.7-9.3 increasing	0.71-0.73 decreasing
29.4.2001	weaker than +6.00	<1	0.80-0.81 decreasing	1.21	20.6-20.9 increasing	0.73
13.8.-22.10.2001	-3.67	82-100 increasing	1.76-2.10 increasing	1.15-23.03 decreasing	8.0-9.5 decreasing	0.71-0.73 decreasing

19.4.2002	weaker than +8.00	<1	0.84	0.49	19.9	0.72
11.8.-21.9.2002	-3.35	91-100 increasing	2.20-2.40 increasing	0.69-14.42 decreasing	7.0-7.6 decreasing	0.72-0.73 increasing
15.11.-25.11.2002	-3.38	80-87 decreasing	1.97-2.10 decreasing	17.49-20.50 increasing	8.0-8.5 increasing	0.72-0.73 decreasing
26.2.2003	weaker than +5.00	<1	0.83	1.36-1.37 increasing	20.1	0.72
7.8.-31.8.2003	-3.67	99-100 increasing	2.08-2.10 increasing	3.26-5.10 decreasing	8.0	0.71-0.72 increasing
16.2.2004	weaker than +7.00	<1	0.81	0.77	20.6	0.72
15.5.-21.5.2004	-3.38	77-81 increasing	1.91-1.99 increasing	20.32-21.76 decreasing	8.4-8.7 decreasing	0.72-0.73 increasing
26.12.2004	weaker than +5.00	<1	0.85	1.46	19.7	0.72
3.7.-15.9.2005	-3.67	74-100 decreasing	1.61-2.09 decreasing	5.12-26.79 increasing	8.0-10.4 increasing	0.71-0.73 increasing
15.12.2005	weaker than +6.00	<1	0.79	1.06	21.1	0.72
7.3.-21.3.2006	-3.40	72-82 increasing	1.79-1.97 increasing	20.46-23.75 decreasing	8.5-9.3 decreasing	0.72-0.73 increasing
25.10.2006	weaker than +5.00	<1	0.88	1.52	19.0	0.72
19.7.-26.9.2007	-3.69	70-84 increasing	1.53-1.76 increasing	22.92-28.28 decreasing	9.5-10.9 decreasing	0.72-0.73 decreasing
14.10.2007	weaker than +5.00	<1	0.76	1.34	22.0	0.72
28.12.2007 - 23.1.2008	-3.42	65-84 increasing	1.65-2.00 increasing	19.59-25.65 decreasing	8.4-10.1 decreasing	0.72-0.73 increasing
24.8.2008	weaker than +5.00	<1	0.89	1.54-1.56 increasing	18.8	0.72
23.4.-25.5.2009	-3.70	64-83 decreasing	1.41-1.74 decreasing	23.42-30.12 increasing	9.6-11.8 increasing	0.72-0.73 increasing
11.8.2009	weaker than +5.00	<1	0.74	1.61	22.6	0.72
23.10.-17.11.2009	-3.45	63-81 increasing	1.58-1.93 increasing	20.97-26.49 decreasing	8.7-10.6 decreasing	0.71-0.73 increasing
24.6.2010	weaker than +5.00	<1	0.91	1.54	18.4	0.72
27.2.-26.3.2011	-3.71	61-79 decreasing	1.36-1.66 decreasing	25.67-30.72 increasing	10.1-12.3 increasing	0.72-0.73 increasing
9.6.2011	weaker than +5.00	<1	0.71	1.85	23.5	0.72
22.8.-7.9.2011	-3.49	64-76 increasing	1.56-1.79 increasing	23.54-26.81 decreasing	9.3-10.7 decreasing	0.71-0.72 increasing
23.4.2012	weaker than +5.00	<1	0.92	1.50-1.51 increasing	18.2	0.72
28.12.2012 - 22.1.2013	-3.71	59-76 decreasing	1.32-1.61 decreasing	26.63-31.10 increasing	10.4-12.7 increasing	0.72-0.73 increasing
5.4.2013	weaker than +4.00	<1	0.69	2.02	24.2	0.73
19.6.-1.7.2013	-3.53	63-73 increasing	1.53-1.70 increasing	25.12-27.39 decreasing	9.8-10.9 decreasing	0.72
21.2.2014	weaker than +5.00	<1	0.94	1.45	17.8	0.72
7.11.-14.11.2014	-3.71	62-68 decreasing	1.38-1.48 decreasing	29.15-30.39 increasing	11.3-12.1 increasing	0.72-0.73 increasing
31.12.2014	-2.98	21	0.83	25.54	20.1	0.73

Made with STELLARIUM and PLANETARIUM.